

Covid-19 Pandemic A Curse or Boom for The Pharmaceutical Industry

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Abstract

COVID-19 has led to various economic issues which have become worse for the whole of the world, especially for the underdeveloped country because of the lack of resources. To come back to this situation there is involvement of the Government, Banks, Managerial Personnel and assistance from various agencies in solving pandemic situations. To grow the Healthcare facilities in the country there are various relaxations provided by the Government and Health Ministry for the growth and innovations and further development of the Pharmaceutical Industry. To meet the huge demand of vaccines, medicines and health equipment there is requirement to change in the techniques of production of drugs during COVID-19 of Pharmaceutical Industry. Various Acts and Amendments played an important role in supporting the Pharmaceutical Industry. There are also various current trends in pharmaceutical industry like Changes created by digital technology, Integrated batch processing, Use of Artificial Intelligence, Use of Cloud Technology and others. There are various conclusions and suggestions for the upliftment of pharmaceutical industry as the current needs of time.

Keywords: Government, Healthcare Professionals, Banks, Schemes, Acts and Policies

1. Introduction

Advanced techniques are being used by the medical professional to accelerate the finding of solution to many threats' disease like Coronavirus. Online platforms are created at the time of pandemic virtual reality, augmented reality, and other immersive experiences play an important role in combating any challenging medical problems through audio- video based virtual communication. With the help of online technology and raising people' s awareness of any critical situations makes it useful for the remote locations to investigate telemedicine, and plan, treat and have control of medical conditions. (1) Therefore, the situation of Covid-19 pandemic placed a position of a curse or boom for the Pharmaceutical Industry. With the help of advanced technology, innovative thought process and by using skill Covid -19 pandemic proved to be boom for the Pharmaceutical Industry. As it is rightly said that "Every worst situation comes to do better".

2. Involvement Of Government in Covid -19 Period

Government played a very important role in the pandemic of COVID -19 as it has sponsored the various schemes and policies for the upliftment of the poor or needy people. Tremendous efforts done by the Government to be involved in Pathogenesis, Diagnosis, treatment and Vaccines planning

(2) control the situation of COVID-19 in the country the various efforts are:

2.1 Soft loan:

Government provides soft loan to the people who are needy and also provide loan to the start-up and entrepreneur professional so that they can smooth out their business cost and expenses which have occurred during the period of pandemic when the company has no business.

2.1.1. Transparent policies: Government provides the various transparency policies which gives benefits to the millions of people as Government transfers the monthly rupees 500-1000 in their account through the attachment of form and Aadhar card so that only the people who deserve can get the help from this scheme.

2.1.2. Subsidies: Government provides subsidies to the various poor people through the various schemes and programs run by the government from time to time. As during pandemic government gives free ration to the poor families they get in 1 month two times ration which includes Rice, Wheat, oil, Chana and salt so that no one people get hunger due to has low income.

2.1.3. Transportation facilities:

Government also provides transportation facilities to the people who lives far from their families for finding out the work or students and job worker. There were various thousands of students who lives in Kota for taking the coaching, people reside in Delhi for getting the job with their families after the pandemic they lost their job and return to their hometown. Therefore, due to this situation prevail in the country Government provides the transportation facilities to the people.

2.1.4. No burden of EMI: During the period of pandemic, the government gives instruction to the bank not to charge the EMI during the pandemic and after the pandemic the EMI can be given to the bank at the reasonable instalment as the income increases. Government wanted to have the people relax free so that they can paid their EMI when they earn their income.

2.2. Online training programmes: -

There are various programmers run by the government at the online stage so that people who are remain at home can utilize their time in a best possible way. Programmers run by the government are:

- Digital Education
- Internet Access under BHARAT NET
- Training programs
- SODHGANGA

2.2.1. Medical facilities

This is the essential element during the period of pandemic as Government has done tremendous efforts to cope up with the situation of this pandemic and which results that Doctors and Nurses work very hard to saves the life of the people in Government hospitals. Government provides facilities of beds, ventilators, medicines, equipment and machines to saves the lives of the millions of people.

2.2.2. Rebate in Licensing

The government gives Rebates to the various licensing policies of the pharmaceuticals company so that more company comes and meet the demand of the market through enlarge the production. In pandemic period it requires the demand of masks, sanitizers, ppt kits, face mask etc. the

government gives rebate to this type of company in getting the license for the production of their work.

3. INVOLVEMENT OF BANKS IN COVID -19 PERIOD

Banks also played a very important role in the time of pandemic as it helps to raise finance, provides financial support and bring out easy return debt policy for the people.

The following role of the banks are: -

3.1. Easy Finance:

Fast growing finance literature explores the potential impacts of the COVID -19 pandemic on financial market. (3)

Banks provides easy finance to the people at the time of pandemic who are suffering from lack of finance and provide cheap loan to the people at large. Banks provides easy financial facilities to the people who can live their livelihood easily without any botheration.

3.2. Online Platform:

Banks provides online platform to the people at the time of pandemic as because of to follow the guideline of the Government and to make the physical distancing among the people. Banks provides various online platform which includes Debit Credit transaction, importers and exporters transaction, Account holder balance, Online payment, Online attachment of proof id for verification, etc.

3.3. Provides Soft loan:

Banks provides soft loan to the household, businessman, and entrepreneur so that in the time of pandemic they can fulfil their basic needs and they can do some business or any other work for earning their

income. Banks charge very low interest at the time of pandemic.

3.4. Relaxation in EMI:

Banks provides relaxations in EMI at the time of pandemic as because people didn't earn any income and some people lost their job also and some have utilised their saved money and become with no money due to all these problems emergence at the time of COVID -19 Banks decides no the take the EMI at the time of pandemic.

3.5. Support Government:

Banks support the government in creating the situation of peace in the economy and diverse the fund further to the public provided by the government. Banks do the work in pandemic situation to transfer the funds in the account of account holder so the people can take benefit from the financial schemes provided by the government.

3.6. Support Business professionals:

Banks support the business professionals in managing their business and cover their cost while pandemic and recover the salary of the employee and various cost associated with the business of the businessman.

3.7. Maintain capital formation up to some extent:

Banks creates the capital formation in the economy in terms of the saving and investment. As the capital formation done with the help of the saving and investment. Saving and investment is done with the maintenance of the saving and investment.

3.8. Provide ATM facilities:

Banks provides the ATM facilities to the people at their doorstep. Banks tried to open the ATM in every district and villages and small-town area with minimum distance so that people who require funds from their account does not bother to go to banks and stands in long ques and then have funds. Banks saves the time and efforts in having money from the ATM.

3.9. Maintain COVID -19 Guidelines:

Banks maintain the COVID -19 guidelines in performing various function for its customers it follows the various rules in the area of banks which are :

- Entry without having mask is prohibited
- Before entering in banks uses of sanitizers was compulsory
- Maintain proper distance while in banks
- Banks staff also have to follow all the guidelines related to protection from infecting from the diseases.

4. INVOLVEMENT OF MANAGERIAL PERSONNEL IN COVID-19 PERIOD

Managerial personnel who are responsible for running the company or any business enterprises has also played the crucial role in the situation of pandemic called COVID -19. During this pandemic situation organization are evolving many engagement activities like online family engagement activities, virtual development and learning, online team building activities, webinars with industry experts, team meet-ups over video conference, online weekly alignment sessions, appreciation sessions, new skill trainingprograms webinars on

dealing with anxiety and stress. (4) The following are the various role performed by the managerial personnel in the pandemic period: -

4.1. Coordination established:

They established the coordination among the various employees in the organization so that they can work during this pandemic situation with the integrity and enthusiasm. They coordinated various diversified employees which comes from different environment which is also a very difficult task to be played by managerial personnel.

4.2. Financial strategy:

During these pandemic times financial strategy is made by the managerial personnel so that important work can be done with the limited funds which includes the cutting of cost, cutting of expenditure and maintain financial standards within the organizations.

4.3. Performance evaluation: -

Managerial personnel played the important role in evaluating the performance of middle and lower-level management so that their working style do not affected by any situation like working from home strategy is followed during the period of COVID -19. Performance evaluation is done by the various performance measuring standards.

5. Assistance From Various Agencies In Solving Pandemic Problem

There are various agencies who has done a great effort in solving the situation of pandemic. The following various agencies are: -

5.1. Mission Oxygen: -

It takes the initiatives to provides overnight oxygen to the hospitals who were running out of lack of oxygen. The aim of this organization is to saves the life of the people who were dead due to lack of oxygen. Members in this organization completes the task as for their core competencies area.

5.2. Gautam Gambhir Foundation: -

It also takes the import ants steps to facilitates the people which includes

- Ration relief kits
- Cooked meals
- Personal protection kits
- Bedding kits
- Nourishments supplements

5.3. Mazdoor Kitchen:

It works for the daily wage workers in North Delhi to provide meals and subsistence and ration kits to hundreds of people during pandemic. It includes dedicated team of students, professors, artists.

5.4. Breathe India:

It takes steps for the fund collection for oxygen it includes group of IIT alumni in coordination with Save Life Foundation.

5.5. Chikka Foundation:

It carried the relief work through distribution of masks, ration, and soaps to some resourceless communities and it also takes meals to daily wage workers and domestic help who were jobless during COVID -19 pandemic. NGO also creates awareness to maintain social distance.

5.6. Access Foundation:

It provides the free ambulance services with presently have 6 ambulances. It also provides ration, free online consultations through the HUM helpline. This is registered NGO u/s 12AA and 80 G of Income tax Act working in COVID -19.

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5.7. Enrich Lives Foundation: -

It focused on hunger alleviation, education, women empowerment, poverty alleviation and public health. It formerly called Annapurna Movement due to which this organization is also involved in the distribution of food grains and meals to the most effected people.

5.8. Khaana Chahiye :

In the city of Mumbai this foundation started as a citizen-led-campaign in March 2020 to fulfil the lockdown problems which includes food demand of the homeless, migrant, workers, daily wage workers, and others.

5.9. Swath:

This organization is committed for health and joy for all founded in 2009. This organization focused ion the improving the well-being of the poor by providing a quality of affordable and high quality primary preventive health services.

5.10. Spoorthi Foundation Coronavirus Relief funds:

It works for the children to be safe and secure and also to learn, improve and bloom so that they really can grow. It works to break the barriers which comes in the life of the children of poor people (5). It provides relief through the distribution of the various centres.

6. Health Worker Participation

Concept of employee participation gained its significance only around a couple of decades ago, its contribution to the Pharmaceutical industry is enormous specially after the advent of COVID-19 period (6) . The involvement of health workers was crucial in a developing nation like India. According to a survey, there were 5.7 million

health workers nationwide in 2018 according to the National Health Workforce Account.

- Allopathic doctors = 1.16 million
- Nurses/midwives = 2.34 million
- Pharmacist = 1.20 million
- Dentists = 0.27 million
- Traditional medical practitioner = (AYUSH) = 0.79 million

The high-level commission on health employment and economic growth recommended that investments in the health workforce be made strategically to promote social justice, innovation, health security, productivity, and output, all of which will hasten the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals in developing nations like India.

6.1. Worker Participation In Management

For an organization to achieve its goals efficiently and effectively, worker participation in management is crucial. This is because these factors—higher productivity, a devoted workforce, profitability, and image improvement—are all necessary for goal achievement. There are several variables that affect employee involvement in management, including: -

6.1.1. Provide Motivation:

The ability to motivate employees to engage in management is a crucial component for ensuring that they have the confidence to do so and offer their views and proposals to management.

6.1.2. Training and Development:

The training and development of workers in the health sector has given them the confidence, skills, and motivation to take part in management. Worker growth and development improves productivity, quality,

and goal attainment, and increases employee satisfaction with his work and employment.

6.1.3. Knowledge and Education: -

When a worker participated in management, they sought to comprehend the issue and circumstance the management was facing. They then analysed and evaluated the scenario using their expertise and knowledge and gave the management the proper solution.

6.1.4. Analytical skill: -

The management process helps health workers develop their analytical abilities so they can properly analyze data and numbers and conclude about problems they encounter daily.

7. Participation Of Health Worker In Covid-19 Period

The health workers actively and truly contributed to the COVID-19 pandemic situation to control the situation of millions of disease victims. The different forms of involvement include: -

- 1) During the epidemic, the working conditions for healthcare professionals were extremely stressful in the hospitals.
- 2) Due to the high number of people suffering from diseases, health workers have had to operate in environments with limited resources such as beds, ventilators, oxygen, and medical equipment, which has led to a shortage of supplies and increased demand in hospitals.
- 3) Health workers have experienced loneliness because of living apart from their family out of fear of contracting sickness.
- 4) During the epidemic in the hospitals, health workers actively participated in administration and management.

5) While caring for COVID-19 patients, some health workers perished because of contracting the disease.

8. Forms of Health Worker

There are many different types of healthcare professionals who work in hospitals and other healthcare facilities. Some of these professionals include:

8.1. Primary Care

First aid is provided by the primary care practitioner for a variety of health issues and checkups. Patients' general health is managed by their primary care practitioner, who also created their care plan. The main healthcare provider is:

8.1.1. Medical Doctors and Doctor of Osteopathic Medicine (Dos): -

They specialize in internal medicine and offer family practice and pediatric services. They are referred to as "generalists" as well.

8.1.2. Obstetrician/Gynecologists (OB/GYN's): -

They specialize in providing prenatal care, wellness services, and women's health care.

They served as the primary healthcare provider for many women.

8.1.3. Nurse practitioners (NPs) : -

They have the necessary training and are nursing graduates. Others work as primary healthcare providers in family medicine and pediatrics. Some nurses are trained to provide women's health care as a common issue, routine screenings, and family planning.

Additionally, they could prescribe drugs based on disease signs. When there were doctor shortages in the hospitals, they

performed the function of a doctor in the COVID 19 times.

8.1.4. Physician Assistant (PA): -

As Doctor of Medicine and Doctor of Osteopathic Medicine, they offer a wide range of services in conjunction with medical professionals.

8.2. Nursing CARE

8.2.1. Licensed practical nurses (LPNs) :-

They have received specialized training to care for the ill. They hold a state-issued caregiver license.

8.2.2. Registered nurses: -

The state has granted them a license. They completed a nursing program and succeeded on the state board exam. Additionally, they receive the necessary training to care for the patients.

8.2.3. Advanced practice nurses: -

All registered nurses must have a license. Beyond the fundamental training, they have additional education, experience, and knowledge. They consist of the following, as well as nurse practitioners:

8.2.4. Clinical Nurse Specialist:

They are trained in specific fields such as cardiac, psychiatric or community health.

8.2.5. Certified Nurses Midwives (CNMs):

They have training in women health care needs which includes the prenatal care, delivery and labor and care of a women who has given birth.

8.2.6. Certified registered nurse anesthetizes (CRNAs)

They are trained for the unique field in the medical field called anesthesia. Aesthesia is the process of putting someone to sleep without feeling any pain while

keeping their body functioning so that they can undergo procedures or tests.

8.3. DRUG THERAPY

Licensed pharmacists have received graduate instruction from a pharmacy college. In addition to assessing health and prescribing medications, pharmacists can. To ensure that you are using your medications safely and efficiently, pharmacists monitor your progress.

Your primary or specialty care provider's prescriptions for medications are prepared and processed by the pharmacist. Additionally, they speak with medical professionals regarding medication dosages, interactions, and adverse effects.

8.3.1. SPECIALITY CARE

Primary care providers may refer the professionals in various specialists, when necessary, such as:

- Allergy and asthma
- Anesthesiology – general anesthesia or spinal block for surgeries and some forms of pain control
- Cardiology – heart disorders
- Dermatology – skin disorders
- Endocrinology – hormonal and metabolic disorders, including diabetes
- Gastroenterology – digestive system disorders
- General surgery – common surgeries involving any part of the body
- Hematology – blood disorders
- Immunology – disorders of the immune system
- Infectious disease – infections affecting the tissues of any part of the body
- Nephrology – kidney disorders

- Neurology – nervous system disorders
- Obstetrics/ gynecology – pregnancy and women's reproductive disorders
- Oncology – cancer treatment
- Ophthalmology – eye disorders and surgery
- Orthopedics –bone and connective tissue disorders
- Otorhinolaryngology – ear, nose and throat (ENT) disorders
- Physical therapy and rehabilitative medicine—for disorders as low back surgery and spinal code surgery

9. Relaxations provided by the Health Ministry for the Development of Pharmaceutical Industry

In the situation of pandemic, the pharmaceutical industry has performed well and the Government has also helped the industry to achieve this goal with easy licensing policy, cheap rate loan, provide subsidies so that the pharmaceutical industry completes the demand of the market within the prescribe time. The various relaxations provided by the health ministry are ;

- Government provides relaxations to the pharmaceutical industry in case of having finance to increase the productions of the organizations with having the raw material, labor, machinery, equipment etc.
- Government also gives relaxations in terms of getting licenses for a very few industries of pharmaceutical sectors most of the industry can run their business without having the license. This is done due to increase the demand of various products

during COVID -19 which includes the products are:

- Sanitizers
- Face Mask
- N-95 Mask
- Medical equipment
- Oxygen
- Government also provides subsidies and tax reduction to the Pharmaceutical Industry so that many Pharmaceuticals comes in the industry and take initiatives to produce drugs and other medical equipment.
- Government promotes health Industry also in terms of provide them necessary equipment and things which they required in treating the patients of COVID -19.
- Government gives support in terms of the providing COVID -19 VACCINES to the large number of people in the country so that the people become fearless of getting infected from the disease.
- Government also supports healthcare professionals by providing them Protection kits and various rewards.
- Government also takes various efforts and made policies and programs for the Pharmaceutical Industry so that they get First Place in the World in terms of Manufacturing drugs and equipment.
- Government takes decision in terms of providing the pharmaceutical industry facilities for increment in the production and manufacturing of drugs.

10. Various Schemes Launched By the Government For The Relaxations

- In March 2020, to reach out the poorest of the poor with food and money so that they can live their livelihood and can buy essential supplies and meet essential needs. The Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Yojana / Package of Rs. 1.70 Lakh Crore Yojana for the poor to help them fight the battle against Corona virus.
- Under Insurance schemes for fight against COVID -19 insurance cover of Rs 50 Lakh per health worker provided by the Government.
- 5kg Wheat or Rice and 1 kg of preferred pulses for free every month for the next three months and extension is also there provided by the Government for 80 crore people.
- As per Jan Dhan Schemes of Government Rs 500 for every month provided by the Government to the 20 crore women.
- Wages are increased from Rs 202 a day from Rs 182 as per MNREGA schemes for the benefit of 13.62 crore families.
- crore poor senior citizen, poor widows and poor disabled extra gratia provided of Rs. 1000.
- Under PM Kisan Yojana Government to front load Rs 2000 paid to farmers in first week of April 2020 provide benefit to 8.7 crore farmers.
- As per construction Worker's welfare Fund Central Government has given order to the State Government to provide relief to the construction workers.

11 Change In The Techniques Of Production Of Drugs During Covid -19 Of Pharmaceutical Industry

There are various changes which has taken place before and after the COVID -19 pandemic.

CHANGES DURING COVID 19 PANDEMICS

- If the outbreak continues from foreign country generic drug producers who exports APIs from China are likely to face supply chain.
- US food and Drug Administration recognized shortage of supply due to short term scarcities.
- Due to the pandemic of COVID –19 manufacturers of branded pharmaceuticals may see a shift in their demand for both the causes as antiviral use rises and other chronic condition.
- Changes in shifts of employees from 8 hour to 12 or 18 hour.
- Changes in the mental and healthy condition of the employees which becomes rush during COVID 19 pandemic.
- Changes in the method of working in the hospitals of the employees fear of being affected by the disease.
- Changes in the treatment with the patients during pandemic.
- Fear of being affected by diseases by themselves and their family members.
- Permanency of work during the period of Pandemic especially during COVID -19.

12 Role Of Various Acts And Amendments In Pharmaceutical Industry

There are various Acts and Amendments which are made for the Pharmaceutical Industry in India are: -

Medicinal and Toilet Preparations (Excise duties) Act 1955
Narcotic Drug and Psychotropic substances Act 1985 and Rules Drug Price Control Order 1955
Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940
Essential Commodities Act, 1955
Patents Act 1970
The Pharmacy Act 1948
Drug and Magic Remedies Act (Objectionable Advertisement) 1954
Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act 1970 and Rules 1975
Prevention of cruelty to animals Act 1960
Factories Act 1948
Minimum Wages Act 1948
Consumer Protection Act with respect to pharmaceutical services 1949
Pharmacy Council of India (P.C.I.) was established under Pharmacy Act 1948
National Pharmacy Policy 2002
Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act 1971

As per the recommendations of DCE, to control the import, manufacture, distribution and sale of drugs and cosmetics, Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940 came into existence. defined by the Drugs and Cosmetics Act 1940.

The Pharmacy Act 1948

“Pharmacy Act “– An act to regulate the profession of pharmacy.

“Registered Pharmacists’ “ - A person whose name for the time being entered in the register of the State in which he or she is for

the time being residing or carrying on his profession or business of pharmacy.

There is a need of the time to have the qualified and trained pharmacist's and their registration in respective councils was re-emphasized by the Health and Development Committee, 1945 which established by the chairman of Justice Bhora. The Pharmacy act comes into existence with the main aim of regulating and controlling the profession and business of pharmacy.

THE PHARMACY COUNCIL OF INDIA

The first Pharmacy council of India (PCI) constituted by central government in 1949. In 5 years, it will be reconstituted. It performs various functions which are as:

Design of the Educational Pattern and Educational Regulations, Standards of Education for Pharmacists'. It also gives the approval or withdrawal of approvals from the pharmacists.

To control the false, misleading uncontrolled and unrestricted advertisements related to drugs which were freely published and claims exaggerated for their medicines. Drugs and Magic Remedy (Objectionable Advertisements) Act, 1954 main aim of this is to prohibit such advertisements of drugs and false claim for the drug or which gives the misleading information about the drug.

11. AMENDMENTS IN VARIOUS ACTS AMENDMENTS DURING THE PERIOD OF PANDEMIC

- Promulgation of an ordinance to amend the Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897 passed by the union cabinet in its meeting held on 22nd April 2020.

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This bill contains the procedure related to situation akin to current pandemic, it ensures that there is zero tolerance in terms of violence against healthcare personnel and damage to property. This Act contain the procedure for the abatement of such violence will be punishable with imprisonment for a term of 3 months to 5 year and with a fine of Rs. 50,000 to 2,00,000. In addition to this there is also compensation for injury or damage to property to almost twice the fair market value.

- Home Ministry has also directed States to appoint nodal officer.
- During the pandemic Government also gives in the rebate of getting license for the pharmaceutical industry only few industries are there who required to get the license for conducting the drug business.
- In domestic market The Indian Pharma industry has grown at a compounded growth rate (CAGR) of ~11% and 16 % in exports over the last two decades.
- The pharmacy industry also get the position of self-sufficiency and real pharmacy of the world.

12. CURRENT TRENDS IN INDIAN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRIES

The majority of global pharmaceutical sales originated in the 'Triad'(US, European Union and Japan) and together they are covered by 80% of the global market. There are various current trends emerging in Indian Pharmaceutical Industry are as follows:

Changes create by digital Technology:

To solve the latest challenges, present in the market the pharmaceutical and Life Science Industry is going through considerable change and creating digital technology. Innovation in Research and Development and manufacturing required new upcoming diseases and medications. Digital technology contains various trends as

- Continuous manufacturing
- Integrated Engineering
- Integrated Secondary Lines
- Cell and Gene Therapies
- Paperless Manufacturing with eBR solutions
- Smart Biomanufacturing
- Digital Twin and solutions

Process Analytical Technology: -

This process is the key to reducing the time in market an approach that creates the medicinal products is in the right specifications in first attempt of testing It creates to turn quality to integral part of production process and ensure flexibility for production expansion, new products and entry into markets.

Integrated batch processing : -

This process helps the pharmaceutical industry to develop and manufacture new drugs and vaccines specially during and after the COVID -19 period faster than ever. It ensures also more than paperless production.

Use of Artificial Intelligence: -

This term is very common and use in every industry. It mostly the use of computer system to perform tasks otherwise which require the human intelligence which includes decision making, language translation, speech recognition, visual perception, clinical trials, fraud detection,

medications improvements, drug discovery and development.

Precision Medicines: -

It ensures production of medication for specific patient diagnosis. It creates a higher level of effectiveness as smaller quantity production for more than one treatment variation. It also requires specialized facilities.

Integration of Blockchain Technology: -

The aim of this technology is to simplify the way as transactions occur and also ensures transparency and optimizing security without third party requirement. This is an essential requirement for healthcare clinics, hospitals, regulators, and other stakeholders. It boosts efficiency and maximize the outcome of research and development.

Smaller production: -

This requires the smaller quality production with high quality of drugs rather than a large production process with lower quality drugs. In this process the Pharma Industry can only maximize the profits with fast production to meet demands.

Use of Cloud Technology : -

It offers an opportunity for integrating the data and support the growth of the Pharmaceutical Industry like other industries. It also ensures the fulfilment the compliances with good practice quality guidelines regulations by the application used in the cloud.

Discounts and Rebates: -

Health and Human Services Government agencies increase the offering of discounts and rebates to reduce the cost of medication due to there is emerging high price of life saving drug. There is going to be emerging

trend in 2022 to do the examination of drug prices and continued scrutiny.

Digital Training: -

For the proper and efficient use of implementation of technology and achieving regulatory compliance Digital training is required. This is cost effective technique to maintain high productivity and overall efficiency.

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